

THE MEASUREMENT OF RESIDENTS' PERCEPTIONS ON THE USAGE OF LOCAL CUISINE FOR TOURISM

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Abstract

Although the role of local cuisines in tourism development is clearly recognized, the number of studies measuring local people's approaches to the presentation of local cuisines to tourists is limited. The aim of this study is to develop a scale identifying the perspectives of the indigenous dwellers living in tourism regions for the use of local cuisine as tourism products. The study focuses on the perceptions of the indigenous dwellers on the development of tourism in the region and use of local elements for tourism purposes. In this manner, data were collected from local authorities and people living in Mudurnu/Bolu/Turkey by using semi-structured interviews and questionnaire technique. The scale validity was tested by subjecting data to statistical analysis. The findings have proved that the scale, which was formed by 24 of 25 obtained statements as a result of literature review and semi-structured interviews, makes a valid measurement of the use of local food for tourism purposes. The view of the indigenous dwellers emerges within the scope of culture, economy, promotion, protection, employment and degeneration of cuisine culture. It is of great importance for the sustainability of gastronomic tourism to identify the view of the indigenous dwellers to the use of local food in tourism destinations. This study has contributed to the literature about measuring indigenous dwellers' view on presentation of local cuisine.

Keywords: Local cuisine; Food sustainability; Gastronomy tourism.

MEDIÇÃO DA PERCEPÇÃO DOS RESIDENTES SOBRE O USO DA COZINHA LOCAL PARA O TURISMO

Resumo

Embora o papel da culinária local no desenvolvimento do turismo seja claramente reconhecido, o número de estudos que medem as abordagens da população local para a apresentação da culinária local aos turistas é limitado. O objetivo deste estudo é desenvolver uma escala que identifique as perspectivas dos moradores indígenas residentes em regiões turísticas para o uso da culinária local como produto turístico. O estudo tem como foco a percepção dos moradores indígenas sobre o desenvolvimento do turismo na região e a utilização de elementos locais para fins turísticos. Desta forma, os dados foram coletados de autoridades locais e moradores de Mudurnu / Bolu / Turquia por meio de entrevistas semiestruturadas e técnica de questionário. A validade da escala foi testada submetendo os dados à análise estatística. Os achados comprovaram que a escala, formada por 24 de 25 afirmações obtidas em revisão de literatura e entrevistas semiestruturadas, é uma medida válida do uso de alimentos locais para fins turísticos. A visão dos indígenas emerge no âmbito da cultura, economia, promoção, proteção, emprego e degeneração da cultura culinária. É de grande importância para a sustentabilidade do turismo gastronômico identificar a visão dos moradores indígenas quanto ao uso da alimentação local nos destinos turísticos. Este estudo contribuiu para a literatura sobre a medição da visão dos moradores indígenas sobre a apresentação da culinária local.

Palavras-chave: Culinária; Sustentabilidade Alimentar; Turismo Gastronômico.

LA MEDICIÓN DE LAS PERCEPCIONES DE LOS RESIDENTES SOBRE EL USO DE LA COCINA LOCAL PARA EL TURISMO

Resumen

Aunque se reconoce claramente el papel de las cocinas locales en el desarrollo del turismo, el número de estudios que miden los enfoques de la población local sobre la presentación de las cocinas locales a los turistas es limitado. El objetivo de este estudio es desarrollar una escala que identifique las perspectivas de los habitantes indígenas que viven en las regiones turísticas para el uso de la cocina local como productos turísticos. El estudio se centra en las percepciones de los habitantes indígenas sobre el desarrollo del turismo en la región y el uso de elementos locales con fines turísticos. De esta manera, se recopilieron datos de las autoridades locales y las personas que viven en Mudurnu / Bolu / Turquia mediante entrevistas semiestructuradas y una técnica de cuestionario. La validez de la escala se probó sometiendo los datos a análisis estadístico. Los hallazgos han demostrado que la escala, que fue formada por 24 de 25 declaraciones obtenidas como resultado de revisión de literatura y entrevistas semiestructuradas, hace una medición válida del uso de alimentos locales con fines turísticos. La mirada de los habitantes indígenas surge en el ámbito de la cultura, la economía, la promoción, la protección, el empleo y la degeneración de la cultura gastronómica. Es de gran importancia para la sustentabilidad del turismo gastronómico identificar la visión de los pobladores indígenas sobre el uso de la comida local en los destinos turísticos. Este estudio ha contribuido a la literatura sobre la medición de la opinión de los habitantes indígenas sobre la presentación de la cocina local.

Palabras clave: Cocina Local; Sostenibilidad Alimentaria; Turismo Gastronómico.

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1 INTRODUCTION

It's seen that among the critical steps of the development of tourism in a region, food & beverage services are especially paid attention. Food & beverage services increase the competitiveness of a destination by adding a unique value to there.

Depending on the fierce competition between destinations, each destination resembles in terms of the characteristics of the tourism infrastructure (hotels, agencies, transportation etc.) that is post-formed with the investments, however, some factors such as food & beverage services distinguish from the others with their differences and customer traction features. Because food & beverage services are part of the original identity that separates the destination from other (Richards, 2002). This situation has an even greater effect with the tourism intended presentation of the local foods.

Local food is a factor that encourages travel to a region, as it provides a significant center of attraction (Briggs, 2001; Hall & Sharples, 2003). A noticeable amount of the expenditures made by the tourist in the destination are spent for food & beverage (Hall & Sharples, 2003). Besides, a significant monetary gain profit is made by the fact that the tourists take local foods as a present for their homes (Richards, 2002). It is also revealed that food & beverage products affect the satisfaction of the tourists from the hotel (Kapera, 2015), the satisfaction of the destination and the tendency to revisit (Kivela & Crofts, 2006).

In recent years, researches on local food consumption have been carried out due to its importance in regional development and tourism activities (Çalışkan et al., 2019). Activities focusing on authentic products, local recipes and culinary identity also attract the attention of actors operating in the field of tourism (Fusté-Forné, 2017). Again, specific to some strong destinations, it is determined that food & beverage is one of the most essential components of the destination brand (Lin et al., 2011).

Local cuisines are one of the important components of the destination brand in Latin America as well as in the world's leading gastronomy destinations known for their local cuisines. It is very important to use local cuisines as a source of tourism supply in South American countries such as Brazil, Argentina and Peru, which have numerous local flavors. Local cuisines, which will contribute to the local people in the context of regional development, have a critical importance in ensuring the sustainability of Latin American cuisine (Fusté-Forné, 2017).

The close relevance of local food to the sustainability of tourism is related to the wishes of tourists to experience local authenticity. Local food

symbolizes culture and destination and has the potential to enrich the tourist experience by providing the tourist with a connection to the authentic values and cultural heritage of the region (Sims, 2009).

The relationship between local food and sustainability is discussed in the following articles (Du Rand et al., 2003; Sims, 2009): a) Increased tourist consumption for local food will increase the multiplier effect by supporting the regional economy. b) Local food demand will reduce the carbon footprint depending on the tourism industry's way of supplying food from the region instead food demand out of the region. c) Local food will continue to increase the competitiveness and attractiveness of the destination as it is an answer that will highlight region specific features in the competition between destinations. d) Concentration on local food will also facilitate the establishment of a sustainable infrastructure in the destination. e) The presentation of local food means the promotion of traditional production, preparation, cooking and consuming procedures established over the centuries in accordance with the conditions of the region.

If we define the ultimate goal of a tourism activity as improving the quality of life in the region (Dwyer & Kim, 2003), we can say that there is no chance for a locally unaccepted activity in the region to develop on a competitive level. It is thought that the support of indigenous dwellers is essential for the continuation of protection activities in the region and it is determined that the participation of indigenous dwellers is essential even to increase the performance of tourism activities (Sekhar, 2003). In this manner, activities involving the presentation of local food for tourism should take local support. Despite this importance, a limited number of studies which try to determine the ideas of indigenous dwellers on the development of local cuisines for tourism purposes have been found in the literature.

The involvement and participation of indigenous dwellers in tourism development can help to prevent the negative effects of tourism in the region. The possibility of transforming economic developments related to local foods into unsustainable activities is always the case. For example; Sims (2009) states that only 7.5% of the residual cost resulting from food production in the UK has returned to farmers and this amount has declined considerably compared to 60 years ago. This situation causes a dilemma that the increase in the consumption of local foods will produce less contribution to the regional economy compared to the past.

On the other hand, in terms of the production of local food in the region, it is a matter of debate whether the ecological conditions in the region had been disrupted or not; or whether the traditional production in

the region continues or not. If the increase in the demand for local food raises the topic of the non-traditional food production and sales methods which are not approved in terms of environmental health, this development will also be limited and local support will remain at a low level.

Although local food is associated with an authenticity as an image, it is also possible that the indigenous dwellers do not lean towards this production if the materials used by local foods, cooking technique and presentation style of the local food do not reflect the traditional patterns.

There is a need for a measurement tool developed to measure the level of perception of indigenous dwellers because of the high importance of local peoples' acceptance on the presentation of local foods at destination. Despite the fact that there are studies examining the attitude of the tourist on local food and focusing on measurement of them (Kim et al., 2009; Kim & Eves, 2012; Björk & Kauppinen-Raisanen, 2014; Şengül & Türkay, 2018; Madaleno et al., 2018; Kim & Choe, 2019; Sthapit et al., 2021; Badu - Baiden & Kim, 2022; Hussain et al., 2022; Kim et al., 2022) and despite the importance mentioned above, there is no measurement tool for the quality, quantity, process and content of local food presentations through the attitudes of indigenous dwellers.

In this study, indigenous dwellers' view on the use of local food for tourism is discussed and a) It is tried to identify the attitudinal variables that determine this view, b) a scale is developed to determine the level of attitude of indigenous dwellers through certain variables. Scale development study is carried out by data collected from a region (Mudurnu/Bolu/Turkey) which is a rich region in terms of local food in Turkey and a region that begins to develop in terms of tourism by demonstrating this wealth in recent years' mindset within the scope of risk perception for.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Importance of Local Cuisine in Terms of Tourism

It's seen that the studies on the benefits of local food & beverage products to tourism destination primarily interpret these benefits in the four major scopes: a) The destination-specific food & beverage products open the door to a unique tourist experience. According to these studies, food is an important economic and cultural source that provides tangible benefits for tourism (Buiatta, 2011).

In particular, the local food that forms the core of the moral heritage (Okumuş, Okumuş, & McKercher, 2007) is an important requirement for the local culture to be perceived by tourists (Kim & Eves, 2012). It is a

unique opportunity for tourists to try the local foods in their original place in order to understand the local culture and to be informed about the different cultures (Kim & Eves, 2012; Kim et al., 2009; du Rand et al., 2003).

According to Renko, Renko & Polonijo (2010), encouraging tourists to participate in the process of preparing and experiencing local food can add value to the products by enriching the tourist experience. (b) Food & beverage products -depending on the original value- offer a serious preference/purchase motivation for the purchase of the destination by tourists. As a result of many researches, it is revealed that local foods are a factor of attractiveness in tourists' destination selection process and have an effect of motivational source (Au & Law, 2002; Kim et al., 2009; Mak, Lumbers, Eves & Chang, 2012; Kim & Eves, 2012).

(c) Local food & beverage products provide additional income to the region by encouraging purchase outside the traditional tourism product. While Everett and Aitchison (2008) found that tourists are ready to pay more for local food products; as a result of their study, Skarus et al. (2006) conclude that the price of local foods and food products purchased for use in home cooking by about two thirds of visitors is higher than the travel and leisure expenses of them.

(d) Local food & beverage increase the competitiveness of the destination depending on the above benefits (Telfer & Wall, 1996; du Rand et al., 2003). While these products strengthen the current tourism product, they also create a market for these products in the eye of visitors (Boyne, et al., 2003). Using unique features of a destination such as local products and local events helps differentiation of destinations from its rivals (Haven-Tang & Jones, 2006).

In many tourism destinations of the world, local cuisines are very important in creating a positive image through gastronomy experience. The emergence of gastronomy as the second best tourism service according to the international demand survey in 2011 presented by the Ministry of Tourism in Brazil is one of the most important examples in this regard.

However, by bringing local cuisines to the forefront, it is possible to increase the income obtained in different tourism activities. This situation can also be exemplified by the preparation of a booklet titled "Brazilian Aromas, Colors and Tastes" in order to present the local cuisine of the city in the 2014 World Cup, which was also held in Brazil. There are many factors to consider in the development and consolidation of local gastronomic activities. In addition to tourist agencies and local suppliers, the support and acceptance provided by local producers and local communities is very important (Martins et al., 2016).

Unique kitchens can improve the image of a country and make the kitchen an important traction element. In this way, for tourists, experiencing local food and touching the local culture becomes an attractive part of the travel experience. This approach not only arouses interest, but can also encourage the preservation of individual characteristics and culture of local communities (Seo, et al., 2017). In this respect, it can be said that the current literature discusses the use of local food & beverage for tourism as a situation that is presumptively positive and needs to be improved.

After all, the determination of the value of the local cuisine by tourists and the planning of the impact of local cuisines on the destination perceptions of tourists are emphasized as a critical factor for the development and marketing of tourism destinations (Guan & Jones, 2015). However, the convenience of the regional dynamics is a question that should be questioned as the other side of the medallion.

2.2 Sustainability of Tourism Based on Local Food and Scope of Indigenous Dwellers' Approach

The willingness of the local residents to be involved in tourism activities takes place when they think that the tourism results have more positive aspects than the negative ones. This triggers the participation and contributing of local residents in tourism development process (Getz, 1994).

The sustainability of tourism activities depends largely on the goodwill and support of the local resident. If the local people think positively about tourism, then they are willing to shop with tourists and this contributes to the development of tourism.

In the planning of tourism, the opinion of local residents should be consulted and their support should be taken. Thus, it will be possible to eliminate the negative behaviors and barriers of the local residents (Yoon et al., 2001; Pinheiro, 2014). There are many studies conducted in the literature about the perception and acceptance of local residents' tourism activities (McCool & Martin, 1994; Brunt & Courtney, 1999; Bujosa & Rosselló, 2007; Araújo, 2007; Guerreiro et al., 2008; Diedrich & García, 2009; GURSOY et al., 2009; Lamnadi, 2017; Şahin & Akova, 2019).

As with the development of tourism generally, the perception and attitude of the local people regarding the sustainability of a tourism product based on local food is of critical importance. Considering of local foods in the context of gastronomy tourism will result local supports such as creation of local producer networks, the occurrence of farmers and producer markets, adding value to local foods and sales from field and on-the road stalls (Hall, et al., 2003). These contributions are very important for local residents. However, while

tourists enjoy ethnic and local foods, many of the local residents do not see their own food as special or unique traditionally, and they do not think that this will be something important or desirable for tourists (Du Rand et al. 2006).

On the other hand, despite the benefits of a tourism based on local food, there are some potential threats to sustainability; and the following questions indicate the most obvious threats; a) Can the use of local cuisines for tourism cause damage to local culture? Will the authenticity of the kitchen be preserved?, b) Will the presentation of the local cuisine conflict with the natural values of the region? Can there be crowds that may be the result of this presentation? and c) Will this presentation lead to the transfer of value to the region? Will gain reach local actors?

Remarking the similar problems mentioned below, Du Rand et al. (2006) stated that during the development of the food potential of a destination, the presence of tourists could have negative effects on local culture. Researchers also emphasized that a planned action should be taken to avoid losing social values and to prevent the deterioration of food production standards. To contribute to the sustainability of the destination, he emphasizes the need to prevent the exploitation of the environment and to conduct local food-based tourism activities with a balanced and controlled approach for the development of culture, as well as being a revenue-generating activity.

By development tourism in the region, the local residents will face tourists especially in the places where local food initiatives develop and this will create a unique experience for tourists (Sims, 2009). However, it becomes inevitable that the developing tourism form is perceived positively by the local people to provide continuation of this experience and to ensure that tourists are accepted by the local residents. At this point, the components of the perception of local cuisines should be discussed.

In the literature, the reviewing of local cuisines is largely in line with economic returns. Therefore, the first/most significant perceptions of the local residents on the development of tourism based on local cuisine are in the direction of economic benefit (Du Rand et al., 2003; Renko et al., 2010).

In addition to this economic benefit, it has been revealed by some researchers that an employment opportunity will be created in terms of the production of local foods (Hall et al., 2003). Besides, in view of the fact that some researchers draw attention to cultural corruption, it can be predicted that this phenomenon will be perceived by the local residents in a decisive way (Du Rand et al., 2006).

Another group of researchers emphasizes that the demand for experiencing local cuisines will lead to

a unique cultural interaction and there will be an enhancing effect on the culture of the region in this way (Sims, 2009; Okumuş et al., 2007; Kim & Eves, 2012; Henderson, 2014). On the other hand, it is observed that some researchers focus on the protection of local foods and the sense of cultural belonging of the local residents (Seo, et al., 2017; Andersson et al., 2017).

Moreover, some researchers showed that the presentation of local foods to tourists would be an important factor in the promotion of the region (Lopez & Martin, 2006; Lin et al., 2011; Okumus et al., 2013).

Carrying out a measurement of the use of local food as a tourism product and revealing the views of local residents on this issue are of critical importance to demonstrate the attitude of the local residents in this regard. The commercialization of a product that is the most important part of the culture of the local residents and the use of it as a tourism product is not possible without being accepted locally.

It is essential to learn the thoughts of the local residents in order to ensure their willingness to exchange. In this respect, this study attempts to develop a scale by combining the emerging themes (Culture, Economics, Promotion, Protection, Employment, Degeneration of Cuisine Culture) by obtaining the views of the local residents on the use of local cuisines as tourism products (Table 1).

Table 1. Definition of constructs

Construct	Definition	References
Culture	Ensuring that the culinary culture unique to the society is transferred to the tourists	Akova, 2006; Okumuş et al., 2007; Sims, 2009; Kim & Eves, 2012; Henderson, 2014
Economics	Providing economic benefit and profit to the residents of the local food	Hall, et al., 2003; Du Rand et al., 2006; Renko et al., 2010
Promotion	Benefiting local foods to the promotional activities of the region	Lopez & Martin, 2006; Amira, 2009; Lin et al., 2011; Okumuş et al., 2013
Protection	Ensuring that local food are remembered and protection in the region's culinary culture	Du Rand et al., 2006; Seo et al., 2017; Andersson et al., 2017
Employment	Providing employment opportunities to the residents of local foods	Hall, et al., 2003
Degeneration of Cuisine Culture	Commercial presentation of local food to tourists causes degeneration of cuisine culture.	Du Rand et al., 2006; Sims, 2009

Source: own elaboration from the literature.

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Objective, Data Collection and Pretesting Processes

This study aims to develop a valid and reliable scale for measuring the local residents' point of view for the use of local food as a tourism product. Studies on the local support conditions of development of local food-based tourism are very limited. There was no scale to measure the issue and address the issue with a holistic approach.

Scale development includes the item generation and data collection sub-steps about the subject to be measured. Making a statement based on a theory, making the issue specific and creation of item pool is particularly recommended (DeVellis, 2016).

In the scale development study related to the subject, firstly, a pool of material was tried to be created. A pool of 10 questions was created by investigating the studies (Kim & Eves, 2012, Amira, 2009, Akova, 2006, Lopez & Martin, 2006) in the related literature. After this stage, interviews were conducted with 9 people, including the district governor, mayor, tourism director of the district and hotelkeepers in the district of Mudurnu by creating a semi-structured interview form.

After the interview results were evaluated by the researchers, new items related to the subject were created. From the pool of items created in accordance with the data obtained from the literature review and interviews, a draft of the scale was created by selecting 27 items deemed necessary for the scale. 5-point Likert-type measurement of these items was decided. In order to eliminate the expression errors in the draft, assistance was received by a specialist in the field of Turkish Language and the errors that caused the incoherency were corrected.

In order to ensure the content validity of the items that were corrected in terms of language, these items were asked to be examined by a total of 5 experts, 3 of them domain expert and 2 of them assessment expert. As a result of the opinions of the experts, 2 questions in the item pool were removed from the scale and the item pool was reduced to 25 statements (see Table 3).

In addition, the statements in the item pool are divided into 6 subgroups in the light of past studies, expert opinions and results obtained in interviews. These groups consist of the following headings: Culture (4 statements), Economics (4 statements), Promotion (5 statements), Protection (4 statements), Employment (4 statements) and Degeneration of Cuisine Culture (4 statements).

A questionnaire was prepared with 34 questions by adding 9 descriptive questions to items pool

consisting of 25 statements. In order to determine the readability of the questionnaire form by sample space, it was subjected to analysis of Ateşman Readability Index. This index is used as Turkish version of Flesch-Kincaid Readability Test.

As a result of the measurement, the readability score of the scale was found to be 84,553. This score shows that the scale is an “easily” readable scale (Temur, 2003). Since the research focuses on the local residents and is likely to include persons with a low level of education within the population, “easy readability” of the scale is expected to increase the effective rate of return.

In order to identify and solve the problems that may be encountered during the practice, the questionnaire prepared as a draft was decided to put to pretesting. Between 10-15 October 2016, a questionnaire was applied to 50 people in Mudurnu district center by convenience sampling method and data were evaluated by transferring to SPSS 20 package program.

As a result of the study, it was seen that the average of the answers given to the Likert-type questions was a minimum of 3.74, the maximum was 4.52, and the standard deviations were at least .830 and the maximum was 1.476. It was also observed that the participants did not leave any questions blank. Considering that 19 out of 50 participants in the pre-test have primary and secondary school education (38 %), it's seen that the survey is generally understood.

The population of the study consists of residing people in Mudurnu district of Bolu province of Turkey (Figure 1).

Source: own design by using Turkey's map.

The factors such as being located on the historical Silk Road route, being in the process of being admitted to the UNESCO World Heritage List and being included in the temporary list, being participated to Cittaslow network which starts with the slow food flow as one of the 15 cities in Turkey, being widespread of Ottoman

architectural features in residences throughout the city and being a destination in the entrance phase of tourism were effective in selecting Mudurnu as the study field.

In addition to these features, it was important to have a researcher who worked in this district before and to have opportunities to communicate easily with the participants.

According to official figures, the population of Mudurnu is 19.374. However, 5.082 of this population resides in Mudurnu district center and the remaining population resides in the towns and villages of Mudurnu (Bolu Governorship Official Statistics, 2017). Since no data could be reached at the point of population distribution, it was decided to collect the data by using convenience sampling method, which is one of the non-stochastic data collection methods.

It was reached an agreement with the interviewers about the application of the questionnaire form of which groundworks were completed. In order to eliminate biasness, firstly the interviewers were subjected to training and necessary information was provided during the questionnaire application.

After the related training, the questionnaire carried out according to convenience sampling method was completed in Mudurnu district between 10-24 January 2017 by face-to-face questionnaire method. Data were collected from 680 people. Due to many unanswered questions, it was decided to leave 26 of the surveyed questionnaires out of the assessment.

The multiple normality of the answers of 654 participants was examined. For that purpose, it was availed from the Mahalanobis distance. This method is a distance measurement method (Maesschalk et al., 2000) that takes into account the covariance matrix (Filzmoser, 2004; 18). As a result of the examinations carried out at the level of $p = 0.001$, since the answers given by 39 participants were found as multiple extreme values, these answers were excluded from the data set and the analyzes continued with the answers of 615 participants.

4 FINDINGS

Descriptive statistics for the participants are shown in Table 2. It's seen that the majority of the participants (64.7%) were male and married (69.2%). Another remarkable finding is that 43.3% of the participants had a monthly personal income of 1001-2000TL. While 36.1% of the participants in the study are composed of self-employed craftsman, merchants or freelancers in Mudurnu, when examined according to educational status, it's seen that the primary school graduates are being placed on the top (27,3%) and the high school graduates rank number two (26,8%).

248 from 615 participants (40,3%) stated that they had never take a vacation throughout their lives. 238 participants (38,7%) stated that they took vacation between 1 and 3 times in their lives. Finally, 43.4% of the participants reside in Mudurnu for 31 years or longer. Also, participants residing in Mudurnu between 20-30 years composed of 18.2% of the total sample.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics

Gender	N	%
Male	398	64,7
Female	217	35,3
Total	615	100,0
Age	N	%
18-24	106	17,2
25-34	153	24,9
35-44	129	21,0
45-54	109	17,7
55 years and older	118	19,2
Total	615	100,0
Marital Status	N	%
Single	186	30,2
Married	429	69,8
Total	615	100,0
Education Status	N	%
Primary School	168	27,3
Secondary School	112	18,2
High School	165	26,8
Associate Degree)	76	12,4
Graduate/Post Graduate	87	14,1
Total	615	100,0
Job	N	%

Artificer / self employed	222	36,1
Civil servant	60	9,8
Employee / Worker	153	24,9
Student	21	3,4
Retired	53	8,6
Housewife	91	14,8
Unanswered	15	2,4
Total	615	100,0
Number of Take a Vacation Throughout Their Lives	N	%
None	248	40,3
1-3	238	38,7
4-5	66	10,7
5 and more	63	10,2
Total	615	100,0
Residence Time in Mudurnu	N	%
0-5 years	80	13,0
6-10 years	64	10,4
11-20 years	92	15,0
21-30 years	112	18,2
31 years or more	267	43,4
Total	615	100,0

Source: own elaboration from the research data.

4.1 Construct Validity Study of the Scale

Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) was applied in order to test the construct validity of the scale prepared in the light of previous studies and interviews. CFA method is preferred in testing the construct validity of the scale, because there was a significant deviation from the normal distribution (see Table 3).

Table 3. Normality Test Results

Statement	Skewness	Kurtosis	K-S (p) value	S-W (p) value
Culture				
Presentation of local foods to tourists in Mudurnu offers an important opportunity for local cultures to be understood by tourists (Kim & Eves, 2012).	-1.629	2.721	0.000	0.000
Presentation of local foods to tourists in Mudurnu provides to promote the Mudurnu cuisine traditions to tourists (Akova, 2006).	-1.600	3.458	0.000	0.000
Presentation of local foods to tourists in Mudurnu helps to unite of tourists and local people (Akova, 2006).	-1.419	2.759	0.000	0.000
Presentation of local foods to tourists in Mudurnu is important to show the hospitality of the people of Mudurnu.	-1.328	1.821	0.000	0.000
Economics				
Presentation of local foods to tourists in Mudurnu provides economic benefits to local people.	-1.586	3.266	0.000	0.000
Presentation of local foods to tourists in Mudurnu provides an increase in the value of local food products.	-1.688	3.376	0.000	0.000
Presentation of local foods to tourists in Mudurnu causes local market prices to be expensive.	-0.854	-0.405	0.000	0.000
Presentation of local foods to tourists in Mudurnu helps to increase income from other tourism activities.	-1.417	2.544	0.000	0.000
Promotion				
Presentation of local foods to tourists in Mudurnu is an important tool for the promotion of the people and the region at the national level. (Lopez & Martin, 2006)	-1.330	1.911	0.000	0.000
Presentation of local foods to tourists in Mudurnu is an important element for branding of the region (Amira, 2009).	-1.387	2.391	0.000	0.000
Presentation of local foods to tourists in Mudurnu provides to promote the local dishes of Mudurnu at national level.	-1.180	1.205	0.000	0.000
Presentation of local foods to tourists in Mudurnu enables the local dishes of Mudurnu becoming famous.	-1.490	2.531	0.000	0.000
Presentation of local foods to tourists in Mudurnu is an important attraction element for Mudurnu.	-1.409	2.414	0.000	0.000
Protection				
Presentation of local foods to tourists in Mudurnu provides recalling of the local dishes that are sunk into oblivion.	-1.470	2.770	0.000	0.000
Presentation of local foods to tourists in Mudurnu pave the way for young people to be interested in local cuisine.	-1.199	1.361	0.000	0.000
Presentation of local foods to tourists in Mudurnu allows the local people to protect cuisine culture.	-1.521	2.579	0.000	0.000
Presentation of local foods to tourists in Mudurnu plays an important role in protecting Mudurnu culture.	-1.131	1.490	0.000	0.000
Employment				

Presentation of local foods to tourists in Mudurnu leads to the opening of new refreshment enterprises where local food are served.	-1.101	1.083	0.000	0.000
Presentation of local foods to tourists in Mudurnu increase the number of people who will work in the preparation and presentation of local food.	-1.100	1.294	0.000	0.000
Presentation of local foods to tourists in Mudurnu provides employment opportunities for women who prepare local food.	-1.329	1.884	0.000	0.000
Presentation of local foods to tourists in Mudurnu increases the workforce in the agricultural area for the production of local foods.	-1.256	1.285	0.000	0.000
Degeneration of Cuisine Culture				
Presentation of local foods to tourists in Mudurnu causes degeneration of cuisine culture due to the commercialization of food.	-604	-1.005	0.000	0.000
Presentation of local foods to tourists in Mudurnu leads to a decrease in the quality of the ingredients used in preparing food because of the ambition to earn more money.	-400	-1.260	0.000	0.000
Presentation of local foods to tourists in Mudurnu causes to lose freshness of local foods due to the bulk production.	-517	-1.107	0.000	0.000
Presentation of foods to tourists, that are not unique to Mudurnu, will lead to a degeneration of the local food culture.	-732	-765	0.000	0.000
Multiple normality critical ratio	82.279			

Source: own elaboration from the research data.

The non-cited statements were determined based on the qualitative research results.

There are estimators which will work even in case of violation of normality (e.g., GLS, DWLS, Robust-ML, PLS, etc.) in the test of CFA. Choosing the right estimator is also important in terms of accepting the results of the study. There are also examples in the literature on the testing of the construct validity of CFA (Henry & Crawford, 2005; Ok, 2011).

As seen in Table 3, according to K-S and S-W normality tests, variables do not show normal distribution. In addition, the kurtosis and skewness values of some variables are above the limits of -1.5 and +1.5, which Tabachnick & Fidell (2013) accept to consider data as normal. However, the multiple normality critical value of the data was found to be 82.279. According to all these data, it is understood that the data is not in conformity with normal distribution. In these circumstances, estimators not requiring normality assumption should be used to test the construct validity of the data.

In this study, it was decided to use GLS and its estimators to test the construct validity. The GLS estimator is an estimator that can be used in cases where data is significantly deviated from normality (Singer, 2016) and our sample is in conformity with GLS in this respect. The PLS estimator does not have any limitations with the distribution of the sample, so it can easily work with data that is not normally distributed (Chin, 1998).

The standard load values obtained from the first CFA analysis of the data set were examined and it was found that one question (e3) had low load value and was statistically insignificant ($p > 0.05$). Therefore, the question was removed from the data set and the analysis was repeated. The standard load values obtained as a result of the second CFA analysis were all taken as 0.6 and above values and it's seen that they were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). The obtained results are shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Confirmatory Factor Analysis Results

Dimension	Statement	Standard Coefficient (GLS)	Standard Coefficient (PLS)
Culture	k1	0,667	0,803
	k2	0,754	0,855
	k3	0,765	0,823
	k4	0,836	0,843
Economic	e1	0,747	0,832
	e2	0,662	0,795
	e4	0,718	0,792
Promotion	t1	0,662	0,795
	t2	0,736	0,808
	t3	0,682	0,832
	t4	0,822	0,804
	t5	0,825	0,806
Protection	ko1	0,808	0,835
	ko2	0,7	0,749
	ko3	0,829	0,843
	ko4	0,827	0,844
Employment	i1	0,796	0,810
	i2	0,796	0,853
	i3	0,82	0,830
	i4	0,675	0,767
Degeneration of Cuisine Culture	mky1	0,75	0,833
	mky2	0,945	0,933
	mky3	0,871	0,899
	mky4	0,726	0,824

Source: own elaboration from the research data.

In the established CFA model, it is understood that the standardized coefficient values are acceptable for both estimators. However, in order for the model to be considered valid in CFA analysis, certain goodness of fit values should be acceptable. There is no goodness of fit value that is generally accepted in both GLS and PLS methods.

While many reportable goodness of fit values was found such as chi square/degrees of freedom (cmin/df), GFI, CFI, AGFI and TLI in GLS method; Fornell & Larcker (1981) stated that the AVE (Average Variance Extracted) values for these structures should be 0.50

and above in order to be valid for latent structures established in the PLS analysis. Goodness of fit values (or indices) and their meanings related to conducted analysis are shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Goodness of Fit Values of Analysis

GLS Technique	Value	Meaning
Cmin/df	638,409/ 232= 2,752	Good Fit
GFI	0.913	Good Fit
RMSEA	0.053	Acceptable Fit
AGFI	0.888	Acceptable Fit
RMR	0.097	Model is not compatible
CFI	0.654	Model is not compatible
PLS Technique	Value (AVE)	Meaning
Economic	0,6499	Valid
Protection	0,6705	Valid
Culture	0,6905	Valid
Degeneration of Cuisine Culture	0,763	Valid
Promotion	0,6327	Valid
Employment	0,665	Valid

Source: (for critical values) Schermelleh-Engel, Moosbrugger & Müller, 2003; Hooper, Coughlan & Mullen, 2008; Meydan & Şeşen, 2011.

As seen in Table 5, the AVE values of all the structures in the PLS analysis are above the critical limit. In GLS analysis, while some goodness of fit values shows good fit, some goodness of fit values shows acceptable fit and some values indicate that the model is not compatible. Since all the structures provide the desired AVE value, the model was found to be fit in PLS analysis. When we evaluate the two methods as a whole, it can be said that the established factorial structures are valid in general.

To test the reliability of the structures that appear to be valid, different values are required for GLS and PLS analysis. Because, in PLS analysis, it is recommended to use composite reliability instead of the generally accepted Alpha coefficient for scale reliability. The Composite reliability value of 0.7 and above indicates that the structures are generally reliable (Bagozzi & Yi, 1998). The results of the reliability analysis are shown in Table 6.

Table 6. Reliability Results

DIMENSIONS	Cronbach's Alpha (GLS)	Composite Reliability (PLS)
Economic	0,7309	0,8477
Protection	0,8353	0,8904
Culture	0,8506	0,8992
Degeneration of Cuisine Culture	0,8955	0,9278
Promotion	0,8549	0,8959
Employment	0,8315	0,8880

Source: own elaboration from the research data.

As seen in Table 6, both Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability values for structures are over 0.7. However, removing any of the questions does not increase the reliability values of the structures. Therefore, the structures have the highest reliability values with their available states.

5 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Although it offers opportunities for destinations, the use of local cuisines that offer organic, authentic and unique values in tourism brings serious limits (Cohen & Avieli, 2004; Enzenbacher, 2020).

The approach of the local people to the use of local cuisines in tourism, who are aware of these limits, actually has the capacity to affect both the contribution of local cuisines to tourism and the holistic and sustainable development of tourism in the region (Diaconescu et al., 2016). For this reason, it is a theoretical requirement to measure local acceptance for the use of local cuisines in tourism.

In this study, a scale that can be used for this purpose is presented. In this respect, this study provides a strong theoretical basis for determining local acceptance for many destinations where tourism development is foreseen through local cuisines. An approach and measurement tool that can be used in future studies that will cover discussions on local acceptance is presented.

As a result of the CFA, it was seen that the scale was in conformity with theoretically established structure for both estimators (GLS-PLS). In addition, the reliability values for the dimensions in the scale showed that all structures have high reliability.

The fact that the developed scale produced valid and reliable results suggests that the dimensions compiled from the studies presented in Table 1 also consistently reveal the perception of the local cuisine.

In this respect, the local perception of the use of local cuisines in tourism is perceived in terms of economy, protection, culture, degeneration of cuisine culture, promotion and employment. These dimensions are generally compatible with the dimensions determined within the scope of local perception of tourism (Hateftabar & Chapuis, 2020).

The dimension of culture refers to the interactions that the use of the local cuisine will provide on the transfer of the local culture to the tourists (Kim & Eves, 2012), the promotion of the local cuisine, the integration of the local people with the tourists (Akova, 2006), the reflection of the hospitality of the local people.

The dimension of economics reveals the possible effects of the use of local cuisine on economic gain opportunities, increasing the value of local cuisine,

increasing local prices, increasing the added value of other tourism activities.

The dimension of promotion covers the situations that will be caused by the use of local cuisines in terms of promoting the region and people at the national level (Loperz & Martin, 2006), branding the region (Amira, 2009), promoting local flavors, making local flavors famous, and being an attraction for the region.

The dimension of conservation reveals the expectations about the use of local cuisines, the recall of forgotten tastes, the increase of young people's interest in local tastes, the local people's ownership of local cuisines, and the preservation of the regional culture.

The dimension of employment includes the establishment of new businesses, the increase in the number of people who will work in food and beverage, the creation of employment opportunities for women, and the support of agricultural employment.

The degeneration of culinary culture includes commercialization, deterioration of quality, loss of freshness due to intensive consumption, and deterioration in local culinary culture.

The results of this study show that the developed scale can be used as a valid and reliable measurement tool. Therefore, it is thought that the scale can be used in the studies to measure the local residents' point of view on using local foods as touristic products. Due to the lack of similar scales in the literature, this scale is thought to contribute to the field.

The valid and reliable scale obtained in this study can be used to measure local support for the development of tourism in rapidly developing gastro-tourism destinations. Depending on whether local support is essential for the sustainability of tourism, to understand the reactions of local residents to the transformation of local cuisines into tourism products can be critical for tourism development activities.

In emerging markets (like Turkey, Brazil, Indonesia, Republic of South Africa, etc.), it is very critical for the development of tourism to ensure that residents accept products belonging to their cultures, such as local cuisines, at the point of commercialization. For this reason, it is thought that the scale developed will be beneficial to academicians, stakeholders and public institutions who want to conduct research on the subject. Besides, this scale will be useful in developing appropriate solutions by identifying the developments that the local people have not considered appropriate.

Since the study was done in a certain destination, if the study is supported by different expressions or dimensions for the different destinations that exemplify the local residents' reactions and interpretations, it will be possible to make more comprehensive measurements.

Finally, the fact that the destination takes place in the process of converting local foods into a tourism product and that the local residents earn serious revenues also has the potential to change the reactions. It may be possible to understand whether this change is in question by repeating this scale in an experienced gastro-tourism destination.

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Table 1. CRediT author statement.

Term	Definition	Author 1	Author 2	Author 3
Conceptualization	Ideas; formulation or evolution of overarching research goals and aims	x	x	x
Methodology	Development or design of methodology; creation of models	x	x	x
Software	Programming, software development; designing computer programs; implementation of the computer code and supporting algorithms; testing of existing code components	x		x
Validation	Verification, whether as a part of the activity or separate, of the overall replication/ reproducibility of results/experiments and other research outputs	x	x	x

Term	Definition	Author 1	Author 2	Author 3
Formal analysis	Application of statistical, mathematical, computational, or other formal techniques to analyze or synthesize study data	x	x	x
Investigation	Conducting a research and investigation process, specifically performing the experiments, or data/evidence collection	x	x	x
Resources	Provision of study materials, reagents, materials, patients, laboratory samples, animals, instrumentation, computing resources, or other analysis tools	x	x	
Data Curation	Management activities to annotate (produce metadata), scrub data and maintain research data (including software code, where it is necessary for interpreting the data itself) for initial use and later reuse	x	x	x
Writing - Original Draft	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically writing the initial draft (including substantive translation)	x	x	x
Writing - Review & Editing	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work by those from the original research group, specifically critical review, commentary or revision – including pre-or post-publication stages	x	x	x
Visualization	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically visualization/ data presentation	x	x	
Supervision	Oversight and leadership responsibility for the research activity planning and execution, including mentorship external to the core team	x		
Project administration	Management and coordination responsibility for the research activity planning and execution	x		
Funding acquisition	Acquisition of the financial support for the project leading to this publication	x		

Source: adapted from Elsevier (2022, s/p), based upon Brand et al. (2015).

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